

with zinc through nitrogen of pyridine ring has been confirmed by considerable negative shift of about 80 cm^{-1} in CN stretching vibration of pyridine ring observed at 1400 cm^{-1} . C=O frequency of amide remains unaffected in the complexes which clearly indicates that none of the amides is coordinated with zinc through carbonyl oxygen.

Free carboxylate ion gives two asymmetric C=O bands of high intensity at 1670 and 1650 cm^{-1} and one weak symmetric C-O band at 1400 cm^{-1} . In the complexes the high frequency bands undergo positive shift and the lower frequency band suffers negative shift⁶. Thus, the ir spectral data of the complexes show bidentate nature of oxalato group.

Three bands around 1490 , 1250 and 1000 cm^{-1} observed in the ir spectra of nitrate complexes indicate that nitrate group behaves as unidentate ligand⁶. Two strong bands observed in the spectrum of Zn(II)SO_4 at 1115 and 620 cm^{-1} have been assigned as ν_2 and ν_4 modes of SO_4^{2-} ion in Td symmetry. The bands around 450 , 580 , 960 and 1130 cm^{-1} in ir spectra of all sulfato complexes have been assigned as ν_2 , ν_4 , ν_1 and ν_3 modes, respectively for unidentate sulfato group belonging to C_{2v} symmetry¹⁰.

Low molar conductance values indicate that all the complexes are nonelectrolytes in methanol and consequently confirm the presence of sulfato, nitrate and oxalato groups inside the coordination sphere.

Low LD_{50} values of nitrate complexes indicate that these are most toxic compounds of this series. The order of toxicity is nitrate > sulfato > oxalato. However, two complexes namely $[\text{ZnC}_2\text{O}_4(\text{Nmpa})_2]$ and $[\text{ZnC}_2\text{O}_4(\text{bza})_2]$ have LD_{50} values > 1000 and 1000 mg/kg ip , respectively and are almost nontoxic. Nontoxic nature of these two complexes calls for their further screening against various other pharmacological tests like antiinflammatory and anti-passive cutaneous anaphylactic activities.

Compounds No. 1, 3, 4 and 5 of Table I showed no significant effect on CNS, whereas compounds No. 2, 6, 8 and 9 acted as CNS stimulants. However, compound No. 7 exhibited depressant effect on CNS i.e. SMA and reactivity were decreased. In a few cases ataxia (due to incoordination of muscles), anoxia and writhing were observed. The structure of the complexes and CNS activity could not be correlated because of irregular trend of neurological effects.

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Polarographic Behaviour of N-(α -Pyridyl)-Benzaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone and Its Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Co(II), Ni(II) Complexes

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IN continuation of our stereochemical studies¹ on metal ion complexes with biologically active heterocyclic thiosemicarbazide and its substituted thiosemicarbazones, we report here the polarographic behaviour of recently synthesized and characterized N-(α -pyridyl)benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone¹ ($\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{S}$, abbreviated as PBT) which is irreversibly reduced at d.m.e. giving well defined anodic waves (pH 3.6 to 10.6) with two electron transfer electrode reaction of diffusion controlled nature. Soluble complexes of PBT with Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) are also reduced irreversibly at d.m.e. giving more negative values of $-E_{1/2}^0$. Kinetic parameters αn and $K_{1/2}^0$ are evaluated to correlate the $E_{1/2}^0$ values with ligand concentration.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of 'AnalaR' grade. Standard solutions of the metal salts were prepared in double distilled air-free conductivity water. Triple distilled mercury was used as dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.). A Leeds Northrup manual polarograph associated with Pye galvanometer and saturated calomel electrode connected to the cell through a salt bridge was used to record polarograms.

In each set 2 ml 2 M LiCl in ethanol was used as supporting electrolyte and 1.0 ml Triton-X-100 (0.2% in ethanol) was added as maxima suppressor. The volume was made up to 25 ml with ethanol and mixed thoroughly before transferring to the polarographic cell. Purified nitrogen was passed gently

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NOTES

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA OF N-(α -PYRIDYL)BENZALDEHYDE THIOSEMICARBAZONE

pH	Effect of pH			mM	Effect of conc.			Effect of height of Hg column	
	i_d (μ A)	Slope Volts	$-E_{1/2}^0$ Volts		i_d (μ A)	Slope Volts	$-E_{1/2}^0$ Volts	h_{diff}^2 (cm)	i_d (μ A)
3.6	2.21	0.660	0.40	0.5	0.81	0.326	0.68	6.520	1.80
5.4	2.19	0.636	0.47	1.0	1.34	0.370	0.71	6.819	1.90
6.8	2.17	0.600	0.55	1.5	1.90	0.550	0.70	7.219	2.15
8.0	2.13	0.699	0.61	2.0	2.45	0.610	0.70	7.520	2.30
8.8	2.11	0.571	0.66						
9.8	1.86	0.785	0.67						
10.6	1.83	0.666	0.70						

TABLE 2—POLAROGRAPHIC DATA AND KINETIC PARAMETERS IN POLAROGRAPHIC BEHAVIOUR OF Cu(II), Zn(II) Pd(II), Co(II) AND Ni(II) COMPLEXES WITH N-(α -PYRIDYL)BENZALDEHYDE THIOSEMICARBAZONE

Sl. No.	Metal ion	Conc. of ligand m mole	i_d (μ A)	$m^{1/2}t^{1/2}$ ($mg^{1/2} \cdot sec^{-1}$)	$-E_{1/2}^0$ Volts	$(D_0^{1/2} \times 10^4)$	αn	$(K_{f,h}^0 \times 10^4)$
1.	Cu(II)	0.5	1.52	2.514	0.66	0.960	0.1627	69.992
		1.0	1.65	2.537	0.66	5.857	0.1848	23.461
		1.5	1.80	2.502	0.82	3.950	0.0989	20.940
		2.0	1.95	2.588	0.84	3.109	0.1077	11.912
2.	Zn(II)	0.5	1.82	2.052	1.08	10.591	0.1689	4.382
		1.0	1.50	2.061	1.11	5.934	0.1548	2.342
		1.5	1.60	2.107	1.19	4.170	0.1544	1.081
3.	Pd(II)	0.5	1.54	1.892	0.76	13.409	0.1888	45.947
		1.0	1.59	1.905	0.78	6.875	0.1296	30.008
		1.5	1.68	1.899	0.82	4.718	0.1812	12.445
4.	Co(II)	2.0	1.76	1.914	0.88	3.787	0.1170	10.416
		1.0	2.28	2.210	0.88	8.498	0.1509	193.241
		2.0	2.34	2.285	1.15	4.312	0.2007	263.684
5.	Ni(II)	3.0	2.55	2.289	1.16	3.127	0.1731	47.452
		1.0	1.90	2.360	0.85	6.631	0.1627	10.411
		2.0	2.15	2.371	0.95	3.734	0.1493	4.603
		3.0	2.30	2.394	1.14	2.687	0.1199	2.945
		4.0	2.35	2.385	1.15	2.029	0.1480	0.800

for ~10 min for deaeration. The percentage of ethanol in each case as well as the nature and concentration of the supporting electrolyte were maintained nearly constant, because irreversible reduction of an organic compound may also be affected by a chemical reaction with the supporting electrolyte.

All polarographic work was done at 300 ± 4 K and under conditions that serve to render the migration current negligible. Values of 't' were measured at several different potentials in the rising parts of the wave such that 'i' was in between 10 to 95% of i_d . In the case of Zn(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) studies, $-E_{1/2}^0$ values were determined by plotting $-E_{d.e.}$ vs $[\log i/(i_d - i) - 0.5 + 6 \log t]$, while in the case of Cu(II) and Pd(II) where there was no appreciable change in 't' with potential (preferably below -1.0 V), plots were made of $-E_{d.e.}$ vs $[\log i/(i_d - i)]$. Diffusion-controlled nature of the waves were determined by recording the polarograms at various mercury heights.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic behaviour of the ligand PBT :

In case of PBT well defined anodic waves were obtained between pH 3.6 to 10.6 as observed earlier²

for thiols, thiourea and other sulphur compounds such as cysteine and cystine. All the plots of $-E_{d.e.}$ vs $[\log (i_d - i)/i]$ yielded straight lines with mean slope value 0.655 V, which showed irreversible and two electron transfer electrode reaction³. It is observed that with increasing pH, $-E_{1/2}^0$ shifts to more negative values, while i_d decreases. The $-E_{1/2}^0$ values are found to be nearly the same (~0.70 V) with increasing conc. of the ligand. The polarograms of PBT and its present complexes at constant ligand concentration and identical conditions, but at different heights of mercury column gave a linear plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{diff}}$, suggesting diffusion controlled nature of the reaction. A plot of $-E_{1/2}^0$ vs pH gave a straight line upto pH 8.0. The intersection of the lines showing deviation gave the dissociation constant (pK_a) of PBT as 9.1.

Polarographic behaviour of Cu(II), Zn(II), Pd(II), Co(II) and Ni(II) complexes with PBT :

In all the complexes with PBT slope values indicated irreversible nature of the electrode reaction, which are obtained due to slow establishment of an equilibrium between the oxidised and the reduced forms at the electrode surface⁴, and refers only to the electron exchange between the depolariser and the electrode but not to the mass transfer towards the electrode.